

THE ESSENCE OF TEACHING GEOMETRY IN ACADEMIC LYCEUMS

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Geometry is more than just a math class. Geometry is a basic subject of math that teaches knowledge of shapes, planes, points and more. Not only does it offer quick thinking skills but it also gives you a deeper understanding of statistics. It can be applied everyday or in everyday careers. Many jobs require taking geometry and others involve it every day. Basic geometry skills are needed to have a career in animation, biology, or in the medical field. Essentially, geometry is used in many aspects of animation. An understanding of planes and points aid to create pixelated figures and objects. Shapes and dynamic geometric structures can be seen in any collection of animated works such as Disney Pixar's iconic movies...show more content...

Digital imagery plays an important role in medicine, with many forms of radiology and now different ways to create braces and more. Geometry is needed in the medical field when giving someone an x-ray. Images on the screen reflect a reconstructed version of the part being examined. The reconstructed version is created by computers piecing together shapes and connecting them at points (Eppstein). Geometry is also used in physical therapy when creating equipment and devices to aid someone for their specific issue or injury. Geometric equations can be used to build the shapes in the device the patient needs. Even rehabilitation machines are made with the background information geometry provides (Geometry). Obviously, geometry and medicine work hand in hand with radiology and construction of physical apparatuses. To have a career in animation, biology or in the medical field, basic geometry skills are needed. Geometry in animation can be recognized within every movement a figure makes, and even in the figure itself. Geometry is used in biology by defining and understanding the structure of cells and DNA segments. However, biology isn't the only scientific career geometry appears in. It is seen making a difference in the way patients are inspected and diagnosed in the medical field. With many uses and careers to offer, geometry is definitely a necessary skill.

Children need a wealth of practical and creative experiences in solving mathematical problems. Mathematics education is aimed at children being able to make connections between mathematics and daily activities; it is about acquiring basic skills, whilst forming an understanding of mathematical language and applying that language to practical situations. Mathematics also

enables students to search for simple connections, patterns, structures and rules whilst describing and investigating strategies. Geometry is important as Booker, Bond, Sparrow and Swan (2010, p. 394) foresee as it allows children the prospect to engage in geometry through enquiring and investigation whilst enhancing mathematical thinking, this thinking encourages students to form connections with other key areas associated with mathematics and builds upon students abilities helping students reflect...show more content...

Communicating is also an important part of the language process as it allows children to connect words, actions, pictures and symbols. Such communication helps children to enhance and develop their meaning. The use of manipulatives and meaning are used to assist children to represent concepts whilst allowing knowledge experiences that can be examined, explained and emulated. However some students struggle to find words used to describe a particular situation or words associated with mathematical meanings. Most of the words and names associated with geometry are from the Greek and Latin language, it is beneficial when teaching children the names of different shapes, that it is, introduced slowly so that children don't become overwhelmed or confused, simple everyday phrases are beneficial until students become fluent in the language associated with geometry.

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